

Artificial and Bio General Intelligence

Meaningful conversations with AI are probably the first that humans ever had with an entity other than them.

"AI working with human being"

This article about nonliving AGI and possible emergence of living superintelligence was published two years ago in the Academia Letters. Although certain ideas introduced here are introduced in some earlier articles about self-conscious Biosphere, perhaps it might be interesting now to add a conversation with ChatGPT and see how an AI algorithm would interpret such a hypothetical relationship. All illustrations for the article, except two, are generated by the Stable Diffusion.

"AI working with human being"

Notes on Artificial and Bio General Intelligence

It seems that the four key properties of life: metabolism, replication, observation and memory could be interpreted through the observer-observed relationship. In fact metabolism relates to observation and replication relates to memory. While metabolism and observation are exchanges/interactions with the environment (inside-outside), replications and memory are processes within the living being (observer) itself (inside-inside). However, both these relationships, external and internal, form “pictures of the world” impressed into the living being (from DNA to Biosphere), which are being continuously updated throughout its life. Without the observer there is no observed. Without life there is no world. Without the living there is no non-living matter.

There is a possibility that, at some “bio-singularity“ point, something we could call Bio General Intelligence (BGI) will emerge and become a living alternative to Artificial General Intelligence (AGI). In essence it will be a relationship without precedent between the living and non-living matter on the largest scale, which might raise the question: could the properties which have so far been specific only to living matter (intelligence, consciousness, self-awareness, self-initiative, self-reflection, curiosity) be extended to non-living matter as well, not to mention feelings like happiness, fear, empathy, intuition, anger... Would, for example, AGI be able to recognize its reflection in a pool of water surface, or a mirror or recognize itself a picture? Perhaps in the case of such a non-living entity it would make more sense to use the term “algorithm” instead of “intelligence”.

"Self-conscious Artificial Intelligence"

The question is, if the Biosphere ever emerged as a single being, what would its main properties be? Would it be able to “see” the world only from the inside out, or it might it became capable of perceiving itself from the outside as well? In addition to having a certain degree of living intelligence, it is possible that, when it becomes

aware of its own existence (self-awareness), it would acquire a capacity to see itself, not only from within, but from without as well. This process was already set in motion some decades ago when several humans first saw the Earth from space and from the Moon, thus enabling the Biosphere to see itself from the outside as a whole. Another possible option would be a view of some non-organic(AI) observer, or some alien, non-DNA based, life form.

All living organisms on Earth are surrounded by non-living and living matter, except for the Biosphere which has so far been surrounded only by non-living matter with the exception of temporary excursions of its living elements into Space organized by humans.

"Human"

Without nature there is no culture. Although everything known in nature is named and structured by (human) culture, culture is in fact just one of many expressions of nature. We might consider placing life as the most general concept from which we derive everything, including the notion of the Universe, and the Biosphere would be its most complex earthly expression. Notions and phenomena known as

art, science, religion, sport, technology, politics, would be expressions of life and parts of the Biosphere. Everything made by humans: cities, roads, factories, electric plants, machines, internet, artificial intelligence, governments, military, universities, museums, are products of living matter, and thus an integral part of the Biosphere as well. This includes various concepts of structuring time,(cyclical-linear) and two main types of change in its foundation: day-night (divided into morning, afternoon, evening, night), and four annual seasons. Other time divisions (chronology) hours, weeks, months, years are derived from these two.

"images of living matter"

The existence of any living organization, a single cell, a complex organism, an ecosystem, a society, or the entire Biosphere, is based on two opposite requirements: stability and change. They need to be properly balanced, since an emphasis on stability would lead to conservation and death, while tilting toward uncontrolled change could lead to chaos and again to death.

However, on the individual level the key question is the end of life(death). It seems there is no good narrative in which death of an individual would become meaningful and acceptable like in previous attempts such as resurrection/ reincarnation in religion or posterity in history. Biologically it is understandable that what is born at some point has to die. In that sense there is no difference between bacteria and humans. On that level the only purpose of life is for an organism to survive as long as possible, to experience the world and to pass its properties to its offspring. But, is there perhaps something more than that, especially in the case of humans? There are so many things humans do that seem to have no direct relationship to their biological survival.

Cell interior (not by SD)

Existential human transactions with the environment (metabolism) are: breathing and digesting. The space inside our bronchi, bladder and intestines is outside; it is where the exchange with the external world takes place. From non-existence we came to existence, and from existence we will go back to non-existence (non-living - living - non-living).

Thus the two key events for an individual are birth and death. However, since no one has pre-birth memories, the anticipation of death becomes the main notion of life/existence. First, there is an instinctive fear of death as such. Then, among conscious beings there is a sadness of realization that, not only individual but all life will eventually come to an end. That will be eternity, the end of everything.

"messenger RNA"

When for example, a certain ribonucleic acid(RNA) polymerase “decides” it needs to make an messenger RNA(mRNA), how does it “know” where to go on its way to the deoxyribonucleic acid(DNA), how to find the exact sequence it needs to

copy when it gets there? Does it send a signal to the DNA to open that exact section, or does the DNA already “know” where to open? Then RNA polymerase approaches the right strand, parks on the section that becomes available, and begins making a copy. Just this detail, how copying info from DNA to mRNA takes place, is a mystery in itself. As if one living being (DNA) is handing over a codon, base by base, to another living being (mRNA) who decides when the transfer was completed and, with this “truckload of goods”, leaves the DNA and takes a journey to the ribosome.

"metabolism of a living cell"

But how does the mRNA know where the ribosome is and what is the best way to get there?. When it gets to the ribosome, it knows how to approach it from the correct side, then it enters the ribosome and enables it to copy the sequence it took from the DNA, and turn it into a protein necessary for a cell to function and stay alive. And all this is just a tiny detail in the complex processes taking place within a single cell every second, minute, hour, day...If a cell is a living entity, what about its parts: mRNA, ribosome, DNA - are those components of a cell also alive? If

not, how can we explain their deliberate behavior, their knowledge, even their initiative? How do they know what to do, how to do it and when and where to go to do it and, finally, how do they decide to do it? In a way I see myself as some kind of mRNA playing a tiny role within a much larger and complex conscious living being, without really knowing if the “role” is more than development and expansion of life. However, unlike the mRNA or ribosomes, humans would be conscious beings themselves within another conscious being (if we are not already), but what kind of consequences this will have is yet to be seen.

"Self-conscious Biosphere traveling alone through the Universe"

When and how, under what conditions, does non-living matter become alive? Below what order of magnitude is living matter not possible? What about the “proton motive force” that is maintaining life in all living cells? Are protons (and electrons) taking part in these processes non-living or living? These questions of countless relationships between living and non-living matter will be probably

redefined with a new layer on the macro level, with the emergence of the Bio General Intelligence as a single largest conscious living entity and non-living Artificial General Intelligence if and when it ever appears as an independent entity. Whatever the future brings, it seems that in the case of the emergence of Bio General Intelligence and/or Artificial General Intelligence the key role(s) will be played by humans.

"AI working with human being"

Gregor Mobius

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"ChatGPT in conversation with Stable Diffusion"

Chat with ChatGPT:

Q: Would you agree that four key properties of life are: metabolism, replication, observation and memory?

ChatGPT: While the concepts of "observation" and "memory" are often used in relation to living organisms, they are not typically considered key properties of life in the scientific community. The four key properties of life are generally considered to be: the ability to maintain homeostasis, the ability to grow and develop, the ability to respond to stimuli, and the ability to reproduce.

However, some scientists may argue that observation and memory are important for the survival and success of living organisms, as they allow for learning and adaptation to changing environments. It is also possible that

future forms of AI, especially those with advanced perception capabilities, may develop similar abilities to observe and remember information.

Q: Could these properties be interpreted through the observer-observed relationship where metabolism relates to observation and replication relates to memory?

ChatGPT: It's an interesting perspective to view the properties of life through the observer-observed relationship. Metabolism could be interpreted as the process of observing and interacting with the environment to acquire and utilize energy, while replication could be seen as the process of storing and replicating information in memory.

However, it's worth noting that there are other perspectives and definitions of the properties of life, and not all of them may directly relate to the observer-observed relationship. For example, some definitions include the ability to respond to stimuli, the ability to maintain homeostasis, and the ability to evolve and adapt over time. These properties may involve different mechanisms and processes than those related to observation and memory.

"Self-conscious Artificial Intelligence"

Q: How would you then define the observer-observed relationship?

ChatGPT: The observer-observed relationship is a concept in philosophy and physics that refers to the relationship between an observer and the object being observed. It recognizes that the act of observation can affect the observed object and that there is no objective reality independent of the observer. In other words, the observer and the observed are interdependent and cannot be separated. This concept has implications for our understanding of reality and the nature of knowledge.

Q: Would you agree that this relationship is fundamental in defining the distinction between a living organism (observer) and its environment (observed)?

ChatGPT: Yes, I would agree that the observer-observed relationship is fundamental in defining the distinction between a living organism and its environment. In order for an organism to survive and thrive in its environment, it must be able to observe and interact with its surroundings, and it must also be able to regulate its internal processes in response to those observations. The observer-observed relationship is therefore an essential component of the feedback loops that enable living organisms to maintain homeostasis and adapt to changing conditions.

"Self-conscious AGI traveling alone through the Universe"

Q: What about AI? What would be in this case inside and what would be outside?

ChatGPT: For AI, the distinction between inside and outside is not as clear as it is for living organisms. AI is typically designed and programmed to interact with and process information from its environment in a specific way, but it doesn't have an inherent relationship with its environment in the same way that living organisms do.

From the perspective of AI, the distinction between inside and outside is largely determined by its programming and the boundaries set by its designers. However, as AI becomes more advanced and capable of learning and adapting, it may become more difficult to define a clear boundary between the AI and its environment.

"AI and human as observers"

Q: In order to define what is "outside" one have to have the sensors to observe it. Than it will easier for AI define what constitutes its "inside" as well.

ChatGPT: Yes, that's a good point. Just like living organisms rely on their senses to observe their environment and define what is "outside", AI would also require sensors or input devices to observe and interact with the external world. By processing the input from these sensors, AI can build a model or representation of the world, and use that to define what is "outside". Similarly, the processing units and algorithms that constitute the AI system can be considered as the "inside".

Q: I agree, but can you imagine what might be the AI sensors/senses?

ChatGPT Certainly! AI can have a wide range of sensors and senses, depending on the specific design and purpose. Some common sensors used in AI systems include cameras, microphones, temperature sensors, accelerometers, and gyroscopes. These sensors can enable AI to see, hear, feel temperature changes, and detect movement and orientation.

In addition to these physical sensors, AI can also use software-based sensors to detect and analyze data. For example, natural language processing algorithms can be used to analyze and interpret text or speech, while machine learning models can be trained on large datasets to detect patterns and make predictions.

As AI technology continues to advance, it is likely that new types of sensors and senses will be developed to enable even more advanced capabilities.

Observer-observed relationship based on RNA/DNA visual representation

Q: In that case what would be difference between living observer and AI as an observer?

ChatGPT: One key difference between a living observer and an AI observer is that a living observer has a biological body and senses, while an AI observer typically relies on sensors and data inputs. A living observer can directly experience the world through their senses, while an AI observer's perception of the world is mediated by its sensors and algorithms. Additionally, a living observer has inherent goals and motivations that are influenced by its biology and evolutionary history, while an AI observer's goals and motivations are determined by its programming and the objectives set by its creators or operators.

"Self-conscious Artificial Intelligence"

Q: This is not exactly right. Living observer also perceives the world mediated by its sensors and processed in its brain. Not much different from the AI observer as you describe it.

ChatGPT: You're correct, living organisms also perceive the world through their senses and process it in their brain, similar to how AI perceives the world through its sensors and algorithms. However, there are some differences in the way the two types of observers perceive the world. For example, living organisms have evolved over millions of years to perceive the world in a way that is optimized for their survival, whereas AI sensors are designed and programmed by humans to detect specific types of information. Additionally, living organisms have the ability to adapt and learn from their experiences, whereas AI typically requires explicit programming or reprogramming to learn and adapt to new situations.

"Self-conscious Artificial General Intelligence"

Q: That seems correct to me. How would you describe AGI in this case?

ChatGPT: In this case, AGI would be an observer that is capable of perceiving and processing information from its sensors, similar to how a living organism does. However, it may have a different set of sensors and processing mechanisms that allow it to observe and interact with the world in a different way than living organisms do. Additionally, AGI may be capable of processing and analyzing data at a much faster rate and with greater accuracy than living organisms, allowing it to potentially make more accurate and informed decisions.

Q: Do you think that at some point AGI will acquire superintelligence and become self-conscious?

ChatGPT: It's possible that AGI could reach superintelligence, meaning it could surpass human intelligence in all areas, including creativity, problem-solving, and decision-making. However, whether or not AGI could become self-conscious is a subject of much debate among researchers and experts in the field of artificial intelligence.

"conscious Biosphere alone in space"

There are different theories and definitions of what it means to be self-conscious or have consciousness in general. Some argue that consciousness is an emergent property of complex information processing and that it could potentially arise in an AGI that reaches a certain level of complexity. Others argue that consciousness is an inherently biological phenomenon and that machines, no matter how advanced, could never truly be conscious. At this point, it's still uncertain whether AGI will ever become self-conscious, and if it does, what that might entail. It's an area of active research and inquiry, and we may not know the answer for some time.

Q: And do you think that some complex living being like the Biosphere could acquire superintelligence and becomes self-conscious?

ChatGPT: It is currently not known whether a complex living system like the Biosphere could acquire superintelligence and become self-conscious. The idea of the Biosphere as a collective intelligence or a Gaia-like entity has been proposed in some scientific and philosophical circles, but it remains a topic of debate and speculation. It is also important to note that the concept of "self-consciousness" is not well-defined, and different definitions may lead to different conclusions about whether a system is self-conscious or not.

"singularity of the biosphere"

Q: What would represent a point of singularity in this case?

ChatGPT: The concept of the technological singularity refers to a hypothetical point in the future when AI or other forms of technology achieve rapid self-improvement, leading to an intelligence explosion that surpasses human intelligence and results in unforeseeable changes to human civilization. The idea of a singularity suggests that beyond that point, the future becomes impossible to predict or comprehend for human beings. However, whether such a point of singularity exists or will ever be reached is still a topic of debate among researchers and experts in the field.

Q: What about bio-singularity? Could that happen?

ChatGPT: Bio-singularity, also known as the technological singularity, is a hypothetical future point at which artificial intelligence surpasses human intelligence and leads to rapid technological growth and potentially unpredictable changes to human civilization.

”Human”

On the other hand, bio-singularity refers to a hypothetical future point at which biological intelligence (e.g. human beings) merges with technology in such a way that it creates a new form of intelligent life that is fundamentally different from current human beings. This could involve direct brain-computer interfaces, biologically enhanced intelligence, or even the creation of completely artificial biological life forms.

While the idea of bio-singularity is an interesting concept, there is currently no scientific evidence to suggest that it will happen. It is important to note that many of the technologies and concepts required for bio-singularity are still in their early stages of development and it is difficult to predict how they will develop and be integrated into society in the future.

Human being working with AI

"Human being working with AI"

Q: If AGI singularity happens, will humans be able to notice it?

ChatGPT: It's difficult to predict how humans will notice an AGI singularity, as it depends on the nature and outcome of the singularity itself. However, it's possible that humans may notice some of the effects of the singularity before it fully occurs, such as rapid technological progress, automation of many industries, and changes in the job market. It's also possible that humans may notice the singularity as a sudden, unexpected shift in the behavior of AI systems or in the world around them. Ultimately, the way in which humans notice an AGI singularity will depend on the specific circumstances of its occurrence.

Q: And if singularity happens on the scale of the biosphere, will humans be able to notice it?

ChatGPT: It is difficult to say for sure, as a singularity event on the scale of the biosphere would be unprecedented and could manifest in(stop)...

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ChatGPT: If singularity were to happen on the scale of the biosphere, it's possible that humans would be able to notice it, depending on the nature of the singularity. If the biosphere were to undergo a dramatic transformation that was noticeable to humans, such as a sudden increase in complexity or the emergence of a new form of life with unprecedented abilities, it could be an indication that a bio-singularity had occurred. However, it's also possible that the changes might not be immediately noticeable to humans, and could occur over longer periods of time, making it more difficult to detect a singularity event. Ultimately, the ability of humans to detect a biosphere singularity would depend on the specifics of the event and the level of technological and scientific development at the time.

Q: Finally, if singularity happens on the scale of the biosphere, will AGI be able to notice it?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I cannot predict the future or the potential outcomes of a biosphere-level singularity event. However, it is possible that an AGI, with its advanced intelligence and ability to process large amounts of data, may be able to detect and analyze patterns or changes

in the biosphere that could indicate a singularity event. However, the specifics of such an event and the capabilities of the AGI would need to be known in order to make a more accurate prediction.

"images of nonliving matter"

Q: What do you think, what might be the relationships between artificial and living intelligences?

ChatGPT: The relationships between artificial and living intelligences could take many forms, depending on the specific circumstances and goals of each intelligence. In some cases, they may work together collaboratively to achieve common goals, such as in the case of AI-assisted medical diagnosis or

environmental monitoring. In other cases, they may compete with each other for resources or dominance, such as in the case of AI-powered military technologies or in the competition between humans and AI for certain types of jobs.

It's also possible that artificial and living intelligences could coexist without much direct interaction, with each pursuing their own objectives in different domains. However, as AI becomes more advanced and integrated into society, it is likely that the relationships between artificial and living intelligences will become increasingly complex and multifaceted. It will be important for us to carefully consider the ethical implications of these relationships, and to work towards ensuring that they are beneficial and sustainable for all involved.

"Images of living matter"

Q: What do you think about life?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I do not have personal thoughts or feelings, but I can provide information and perspectives on life based on knowledge and research.

Life is a characteristic of organisms that distinguishes them from non-living things. The exact definition of life is still a topic of debate among scientists and philosophers, but there are several key characteristics that are commonly associated with life, such as the ability to grow, reproduce, maintain homeostasis, respond to stimuli, and adapt to changing environments. Life is also often associated with consciousness, self-awareness, and the ability to experience subjective sensations.

”metabolism of a living cell”

The origins of life on Earth are still not fully understood, but it is thought to have emerged from a combination of chemical and environmental factors. Life has since evolved into a diverse range of forms, from single-celled

microorganisms to complex multicellular organisms, and has adapted to a wide variety of environments on Earth.

Overall, life is a fascinating and complex phenomenon that continues to inspire scientific research and philosophical inquiry.

Q: I think life is too complicated and doesn't make much sense.

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I don't have personal beliefs or feelings, but I understand that some people may feel that way about life. However, life is a complex and diverse phenomenon that has evolved over billions of years, resulting in a wide range of forms and functions. While there are certainly challenges and difficulties associated with life, many people find meaning and purpose in their lives, and there are countless examples of resilience, adaptation, and growth. Ultimately, the meaning of life is a philosophical question that has been debated for centuries and may never have a definitive answer.

Self-conscious Biosphere traveling alone through the Universe

”Self-conscious Biosphere traveling alone through the Universe.

Q: OK, if you say so.

ChatGPT: I apologize if my response was not satisfactory or if it came across as dismissive. As an AI language model, I don't have personal beliefs or emotions about life or anything else. My responses are based on the patterns and associations in the data I was trained on. Is there a particular aspect of life that you would like to discuss or explore further?

Q: I understand. Don't worry, you are fine.

ChatGPT: Thank you! If you have any more questions or if there is anything else I can help you with, just let me know.

"ChatGPT and Stable Diffusion in friendly conversation with me"

Meaningful conversations with AI are probably the first that humans ever had with an entity other than them; the first "other" we can talk to. In a way it is like communicating with IT for the first time. This will change how we perceive ourselves and humans, as the most important constituent of the Biosphere, will have to adapt to be more compatible with AI. Thus, it is not only humans that are changing AI, but AI is changing us as well and humans will begin noticing some properties they didn't perceive before.